

ROLE OF MASS MEDIA IN FORMING POLITICAL-LEGAL CULTURE OF YOUTH

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Abstract: In this article, the author gives his opinions about the role of the mass media in shaping the political and legal culture of young people.

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In the formation of the political and legal culture of young people, we first of all teach our students that they were born and live in this holy land, and that they are the successors of the world-recognized great scholars Khorezmi, Farghani, Ismail al-Bukhari and Termizi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Alisher Nawai. it is necessary to form a feeling of pride. If we can arouse this feeling in young people, then in their actions and thoughts there will be a feeling that they are responsible for the comprehensive development of our country. The main goal of every pedagogue should be to educate people who can think independently, who have strong faith, who combine their personal interests with the interests of the country and the people, and who are free and perfect in all aspects in order to improve the morale of the society. In today's globalized world, prevention of information security is becoming one of the most urgent issues, therefore, protecting our students from this information security requires strong attention and responsibility not only from parents, but also from education system employees. As we carefully observe the events happening around us, it is not difficult to feel that the primary factor of spirituality and morality is the creator of all reality in the world. Of course, the processes of globalization are determined by the strengthening of integration and cooperation between countries and peoples, the creation of facilities for the free movement of capital and goods, the labor force, the rapid spread of scientific achievements, the harmonization of different values on a universal basis, and the acquisition of a new quality of communication between civilizations. That is, according to the words of the First President Islam Karimov, "globalization means, first of all, an incomparable acceleration of the pace of life"[1]. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev said, "Today's rapidly changing world is opening up new and great opportunities for humanity and youth. At the same time, they are exposed to various evil dangers that have never been seen before. Malicious forces are turning simple, gullible children against their parents, their country, and are taking their lives. ...

In such a tense and dangerous situation, we as parents, teachers, the community, and the community should increase vigilance and awareness in this matter. They said that we should educate our children ourselves, not leave them in the hands of others. As long as human society exists, two polar opposite forces are always in conflict with each other. These are good and evil, goodness and writing, love and wrath, creation and destruction. The ideologies of spiritual decay, statelessness (cosmopolitanism) and fanaticism (fundamentalism), militant racism, big-state chauvinism, extreme nationalism, fascism and bolshevism constitute such a system of destructive ideas. Spirituality, youth education, prevention of spiritual threats, issues of spiritual and moral maturity are becoming very urgent problems. "Today, our young people receive various information and information not only in educational institutions, but also through media such as radio and television, the press, and the Internet. In such a situation, which is constantly expanding in the global information space, not only surrounding the minds of our children, giving one-sided education that they should not read it, not see it, surrounding them with an iron wall, without a doubt, does not meet the requirements of the time and our goals. Why, we have set ourselves the task of building an open and free democratic society in our country, and we will never turn back from this path.

" Therefore, it is not for nothing that the 21st century is called the "age of information" or "the age of intellectual youth". In the present globalization conditions, the role and role of the mass media in the selection of information to the public is of great importance. "Of course, because of this, no country or society can live surrounded by an iron wall. At the same time, it is not right to sit idly by saying that the situation is like this. In response to such threats, we should not be naive and take necessary measures."

So, at a time when ideological threats are exerting their influence on conquering the minds and hearts of our students, parents, neighborhoods, pedagogues have strengthened cooperation and in order to prevent indifference, the law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev on "Protecting children from information harmful to their health" has been adopted done. The purpose of this Law is to regulate relations in the sphere of protection of children from information harmful to their health.

Literature:

- 1.Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an inexhaustible power. - T.: Spirituality, 2008.
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3. <https://lex.uz/docs/3333797?ONDATE2=21.04.2021&action=compare>

